

Knowledge and Perception Regarding Caesarean Section Delivery and Its Determining Factors Among Married Women of Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City

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ABSTRACT

Background: A Cesarean section (CS) is a surgical procedure that can save the lives of mothers and babies when certain complications arise during pregnancy or labor. This research study assessed the knowledge level, perception and various determining factors for caesarean section among married women of reproductive age.

Method: A Cross-sectional study was conducted among 349 married women of Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City. The mixed method was used in this study; where face to face interviews were taken through semi-structured questionnaire and Likert scale for quantitative data and Key Informant Interview (KII) was completed with the obstetricians for qualitative data. Data collection was done in kobo tool which was generated to SPSS VS.20 and analyzed using Chi-square test and logistic regression for knowledge level and Man-Whitney test(U) and Kruskal–Wallis(H) test for perception where association were established with p value <0.05.

Results: Nearly six out of ten (59%) had adequate knowledge regarding caesarean section. Factors such as religion, education, gravida, previous place and previous mode of delivery were associated with the level of knowledge. In this study, respondents who had experienced previous CS and normal as well as CS were 2.822 (p=0.002) and 2.578 (p= 0.030) times respectively more likely to have adequate knowledge than those with previous normal delivery. The prevalence of CS was found to be 32.9% among the studied population. Major factors such as preferred mode and previous mode of delivery were associated with the perception. The median of perception was significantly higher among respondents who had previous experience of CS than the group who haven't.

Conclusion: The findings indicated that most respondents had sufficient knowledge about cesarean sections (CS), despite the increasing prevalence of the procedure. Respondents who had previously undergone a CS had a greater awareness of the procedure compared to those who had a normal vaginal delivery (NVD). Consequently, stakeholders at all levels of government should be held accountable for ensuring the quality and effectiveness of maternal and child health services provided by healthcare institutions.

KEYWORDS: Caesarean Section, Delivery, Knowledge, Perception, Married women

INTRODUCTION

A Cesarean section (CS) is a surgical procedure that can save the lives of mothers and babies when certain complications arise during pregnancy or labor.¹ The fetal delivery through an open abdominal incision (Laparotomy) and an incision in the uterus (Hysterectomy) is generally termed as a Caesarean section.²

According to World Health Organization 1985, 10 to 15 percent (10 to 15 C-sections per 100 live births) is the upper limit that should be adhered to by nations in order to achieve the best outcomes for both the mother and their newborns.³ Medical professionals typically perform C-sections when vaginal delivery is considered unsafe or not possible.⁴ The decision to perform a C-section is made by healthcare professionals based on careful; evaluation of the risks and benefits in each individual case.⁵ Caesarean section, when carried out according to the right guidelines, it greatly lowers newborn and maternal morbidity and death, but when carried out incorrectly, it can be harmful to both the mother and the child. ⁶ CS increases the risk of non-communicable illnesses and immune-related problems among newborns later in life while exposing both the mother and the baby to a number of unwanted short

term and long-term consequences.^{6,7} The most common medical reasons that a doctor may recommend a C-section include situations where vaginal delivery would pose a risk to the health of the mother or baby.

According to NDHS 2022 report, of the total number of live births and/or stillbirths in the 2 years preceding the survey, 18% were delivered via C-section.⁸ The proportion has increased steadily from over time, from 1% in 1996 to 10% in 2016 and 18% in 2022.⁸ CS performed in private health facilities (51%) are more than three times in that for government health institutions (15%).⁸ Additionally, the annual report 2079/80 the national average CS was 25% among the reported deliveries which has increased by 3% and 5% points compared to the last two fiscal years.⁹

The new research from the World Health Organization (WHO) reveals that the global rate of CS is accounting for more than 1 in 5 (21%) of all childbirths, which is projected to increase further, with nearly a third (29%) of all births likely to take place by CS by 2030.⁷ Previous CS is a major factor that increases the likelihood of having a repeated caesarean.^{10,11} Vaginal birth after caesarean (VBAC) can be attempted in some cases but many women opt for repeat CS.^{10,11} A study conducted among South and South East Asian women highlighted the higher prevalence of C-section among urban women compared to rural women and the influence of maternal socioeconomic characteristics, such as education level and place of delivery, on the preference for C-section.¹² The cross-sectional study at tertiary care center of Nepal revealed 44.22% of CS deliveries where 76.9% were due to the emergency indications.¹³ One of the cross-sectional study of Jeddah, Saudi Arabia concluded that most participants received a poor knowledge score for the awareness of Cesarean section complications (45.4%), and only 12.6% had good knowledge.¹⁴ Though most participants were university-educated and had an excellent socioeconomic status.¹⁴

A literature on Perception of pregnant women towards caesarean section in Nigeria, revealed that expectant mothers had predominantly negative and low perception on CS.¹⁵ Specifically, more than three fourth (79%) of participants expressed objection to delivery via CS due to the fear of mortality and nearly two third (60%) cited the expenses as the basis for their objections.¹⁵ The findings from study on factors influencing decision making to accept elective Caesarean section on Ghana among 1 63 purposively-sampled postnatal women in a hospital which concluded that the major as the support from husband/partner/relatives (39.3%), their baby's life being at risk (24.5 %), history of previous CS and knowledge about the procedure (19.6 %).¹⁶ The findings also showed that women's decision-making in consultation with relatives is the main influencer to accept elective caesarean section.¹⁶

A qualitative study from Bangladesh on assessing women's attitude reported that women from rural community has strong preference for vaginal birth.¹⁷ Recent study from Armenia revealed that financial incentives, maternal request for CS and lack of regulation are the prime factors contributing in increasing rates of CS.¹⁸

METHODS AND MATERIALS

Study Type and method

A descriptive, cross-sectional study was conducted using mixed method in this research. Quantitative research method was used to assess the knowledge and perception regarding CS where data was collected through semi- structured questionnaires and Likert scale whereas qualitative research method was conducted to explore more about the concept of obstetricians to understand whether or not it supports the findings of quantitative data.

Study settings and period

The study was conducted in Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan city, Makwanpur district of Bagmati province, Nepal. The data collection time for this research was ranging from 21st October 2023 to 10th February 2024.

Study Population

The study population for the quantitative study were married women of reproductive age residing in Hetauda and that for qualitative study were obstetricians.

Sample Size

To determine the sample size, following formula for finite population was used:

$$n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{d^2 + \frac{Z^2 pq}{N}}$$

Taking the 10 % as non-response rate, the final sample size was 349.

Sampling Technique:

Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City was purposively selected as the study area. Of the 19 wards in the city, 30% (which equates to 6 wards) were chosen using a lottery method. In each selected ward, a probability proportionate sampling method was employed to reach married women of reproductive age (15-49).

Data collection tools and techniques

The quantitative data was collected using Semi-Structured questionnaire and Likert Scale through semi structured interview technique and the qualitative data was obtained through Key Informant Interview (KII) using KII guidelines.

Pretesting the data collection tools

The questionnaire was pretested on 10% of the sample population in Lalitpur Metropolitan City. Based on the pretest results, several reforms and modifications were made to the questionnaires.

Data Management and statistical analysis

Quantitative: Data collection was done using kobo application from mobile phone. The collected data were extracted to Microsoft excel and then to generated to SPSS Version 20 which was further analyzed.

Qualitative: The verbatim transcription was done on qualitative information which was translated from Nepali to English for analysis. The narrative summary based on the KII guidelines were prepared as output for qualitative data collection.

Ethical consideration

Ethical approval was obtained from Institutional Review Committee of Manmohan Memorial Institute of Health Sciences (Ref No. NECO/IRC/080/029). The approval to conduct the study was taken from the Hetauda Sub-Metropolitan City.

RESULTS

Altogether, 349 women of reproductive age participated in this study.

Table 1: Sociodemographic Characteristics

Characteristics	Category	Frequency(n=349)	Percentage
Age (In completed years)	20-29	127	36.4
	30-39	174	49.9
	40-49	48	13.8
Ethnicity	Brahmin	60	17.2
	Chhetri	99	28.4
	Dalit	32	9.2
	Madhesi	23	6.6
	Muslim	11	3.2
	Janajati	124	35.5
Education of women	No education	50	14.3
	Basic education (1-8)	86	24.6
	Secondary education (9-12)	170	48.7
	More than secondary education (13 and above)	43	12.3
Place of Residence	Semi-urban	153	43.8
	Urban	196	56.2

The table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents according to their demographic characteristics. Out of 349 respondents, almost halves (49.9%) belonged to the age group 30-39 years and least were of age group 40-49 (13.8%). Among all, majority with more than a third (35.5%) were Janajati and least participation was from Muslim (3.2%). Nearly half (48.7%) of the respondents had completed secondary level education while 14.3% had no secondary education.

Table 2: Previous mode and place of delivery

Characteristics		Category	Frequency (n=349)	Percentage
Previous Place of delivery	of	Home	34	9.7
		Health institution	315	90.3
Previous Mode of delivery	of	Normal delivery	229	65.6
		Delivery using Forceps and vacuum	5	1.4
		Caesarean Section	78	22.3
		Normal and CS	37	10.6

According to the Table 2, majority (90.3%) reported previous place of delivery to be health institution. Almost two third (65.6%) reported normal delivery followed by CS (22.3%), both type (10.6%) and a smaller percentage (1.4%) of deliveries were conducted using forceps and vacuum. It depicts the prevalence to be almost one third (32.9%). *The obstetricians expressed, “the inability to perform Trial of Labor After Caesarean (TOLAC) as one of the primary reasons for increasing caesarean section. They mentioned; TOLAC needs well equipped health facilities, extensively trained human resources and appropriate hospital setup to function, whereas our country has limited resources to operate.*

Table 3: Level of Knowledge

Characteristics	Category	Frequency (n=349)	Percentage
Level of knowledge	Inadequate knowledge	143	41
	Adequate knowledge	206	59

Median ± IQR= 17±4

The above table showed that nearly six out of ten of the respondents had adequate knowledge regarding caesarean section. *The healthcare provider shared some myths and misconceptions regarding CS from community people. “In some cases of complications in natural birth, pregnant women and their family members deny for procedure of vacuum delivery as they think it will affect their child’s brain and they tend to request for CS and sometimes even resulting to conflict with the obstetricians.”*

Table 4: Association of knowledge level with sociodemographic characteristics

Factors	Category	Level of Knowledge		Chi-Square	p-value
		Adequate Knowledge n (%)	Inadequate Knowledge n (%)		
Gravida	Primigravida	82 (66.7)	41 (33.3)	4.585	0.032*
	Multigravida	124 (54.9)	102 (45.1)		
Previous place of delivery	Home	8 (23.5)	26 (76.5)	19.625	<0.001*
	Health Institution	198(62.9)	115(49.1)		
Previous mode of delivery	Normal	119 (50.9)	115 (49.1)	20.258	<0.001*
	Caesarean Section	61 (78.2)	17 (21.8)		
	Both type	26 (70.3)	11 (29.7)		
Previous pregnancy related problem	Yes	24 (54.5)	20 (45.5)	0.518	0.418
	No	182 (59.7)	123 (40.3)		

Table 4 interprets that the level of knowledge is associated with respondent’s religion (p=0.016), education (p<0.001) and their residence (p=0.010). The study revealed that there is no any association of knowledge with age of respondents.

Table 5: Association of knowledge level with obstetric factors

Factors	Category	Level of knowledge		Chi-Square	p-value
		Adequate Knowledge n (%)	Inadequate Knowledge n (%)		
Age completed years)	20-29	83(65.4)	44(34.6)	4.046	0.132
	30-39	99 (56.5)	75 (43.1)		
	40-49	24(50)	24(50)		
Religion	Hindu	175 (62.7)	104 (37.3)	8.244	0.016*
	Buddhism	21 (42)	29 (58)		
	Others	10(50)	10(50)		
Education of women	No education	16 (32)	34 (68)	22.67	<0.001*
	Basic education (1-8)	46 (53.5)	40 (46.5)		
	Secondary education (9-12)	115 (67.6)	55 (32.4)		
	More than secondary education (13 and above)	29 (67.4)	14 (32.6)		
Residence	Semi-Urban	102 (66.7)	51 (33.33)	6.577	0.010*
	Urban	104 (53.1)	92 (46.5)		

The given table depicts that gravida, previous place of delivery and previous mode of delivery has strong association with knowledge of CS with the significance of p= 0.032, p=0.032 and p=0.000 respectively.

Table 6: Binary and multiple logistic regression of knowledge level with associated variables

Characteristics	COR	95% CI	p-value	AOR	95% CI	p-value
Religion						
Hindu	1.683	0.678-4.178	0.262	0.849	0.291-2.474	0.764
Buddhism	0.724	0.256-2.051	0.543	0.321	0.093- 1.100	0.070
Others	Ref			Ref		
Education of women						
No education	Ref			Ref		
Basic education (1-8)	2.444	1.178-5.070	0.016*	1.182	0.482-2.896	0.715
Secondary education (9-12)	4.443	2.261-8.731	<0.001*	2.024	0.794-5.158	0.140
More than secondary education (13 and above)	4.402	1.841-10.525	0.001*	1.959	0.615-6.240	0.255
Residence						
Semi-urban	1.769	1.142-2.741	0.011*	3.848	2.103-7.043	<0.001*
Urban	Ref			Ref		
Gravida						
Primigravida	1.645	1.041-2.599	0.033*	1.689	2.103-7.043	0.09
Multigravida	Ref			Ref		
Previous place of delivery						
Home	Ref			Ref		
Health Institution	5.5	2.411-12.547	<0.001*	3.729	1.396-9.958	0.009*
Previous mode of delivery						
Normal	Ref			Ref		
Caesarean section	3.468	1.912-6.290	<0.001*	2.822	1.455-5.476	0.002*
Normal as well as CS	2.284	1.079-4.836	0.031*	2.578	1.096-6.062	0.030*

Others= Christianity and Islam, Ref= Reference group, COR=Crude Odds Ratio

AOR= Adjusted Odds Ratio, CI= Confidence Interval

Table 6 represents the simple binary and multiple logistic regression of variables with knowledge on CS delivery. Those variables that had the significant association with knowledge on CS delivery were further analyzed where Crude odds ratio and Adjusted odds ratio were calculated.

The odds of having adequate knowledge among respondents who followed Hindu religion were 0.849 (95% CI 0.291-2.474 p-value= 0.764) and Buddhism were 0.321 (95% CI 0.093- 1.100 p-value=0.070) times less likely than any other religion. Primigravida women had 1.689 times more knowledge on CS than multigravida. Interestingly, the odds of having adequate knowledge were 3.848 (p=< 0.001) times higher among women from semi-urban than urban area.

The table indicates that respondents who had previous health institution delivery were 3.729 (p=0.009) times more likely to have adequate knowledge than others with previous home delivery. It shows that the respondents who had previous Caesarean section were 2.822 (p=0.002) times and who had experienced both normal as well as Caesarean section were 2.578 (p= 0.030) times more likely to have adequate knowledge on Caesarean section delivery than those women with previous normal vaginal delivery.

Table 7: Perception and Sociodemographic factors

Characteristics	Category	n	Median	Mean rank	U/H value	p-value	U/H
Age	≤ 29	127	74	189.26	4.727	0.094	
	30-39	174	72	169.88			
	≥ 40	48	69	155.82			
Ethnicity	Brahmin	60	74	189.66	15.222	0.009*	
	Chhetri	99	74	192.90			
	Dalit	32	73	162.00			
	Madhesi	23	76	201.85			
	Muslim	11	65	105.68			
	Janajati	124	72	158.14			
Religion	Hindu	279	73	178.13	5.578	0.134	
	Buddhism	50	73	171.48			
	Christianity	9	75	182.33			
	Islam	11	65	105.68			
Education of women	No education	50	68	114.38	26.692	<0.001*	
	Basic education (1-8)	86	73	167.13			
	Secondary education (9-12)	170	74	187.83			
	More than secondary education (13 and above)	43	75	210.50			
Education of husband	No education	22	71	137.80	13.717	0.003*	
	Basic education (1-8)	79	70	145.86			
	Secondary education (9-12)	180	74	185.59			
	More than a secondary education (13 and above)	68	74	192.85			
Residence	Semi-Urban	153	70	143.87	10230.500	<0.001*	
	Urban	196	75	199.30			

Value= Mann-Whitney Test/ Kruskal Wallis Test

The table 7 presents the perception of respondent's towards Caesarean section with respect to different characteristics. The median score of perception was significantly higher among women of age group below 30 (74). Madhesi women (76) had highest score of perception whereas lowest was found among Muslims (65) which was statistically significant (p=0.009). While comparing, the

highest score on medians of perception was observed among women of educational status more than secondary level (75) and least among those with no education (68) which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). Additionally, women residing in urban area had a significantly higher median perception score (75) compared to those from semi-urban areas (70) with the significance of ($p < 0.001$).

Table 8: Perception and personal factors

Characteristics	Category	n	Median	Mean rank	U/H value	p-value
Preferred mode of delivery	Natural	339	73	170.26	88.000	<0.001*
	Elective CS	10	96	335.70		
Preferred place of delivery	Home	2	62	37.25	71.500	0.053
	Health Institution	347	73	175.79		
Preferred health institution	Public hospitals	181	71	146.53	10051.50	<0.001*
	Private hospitals	166	76	203.95		

U/H Value = Mann-Whitney Test/ Kruskal Wallis Test

The median of perception was significantly higher among the women who preferred Elective Caesarean section (96) being statistically significant ($p < 0.001$) can be observed from Table 8. Furthermore, on preference of health institution for child delivery, the higher score was reported among the mothers preferring private hospitals (76) than public hospitals (71) which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). During the KII interview with obstetricians, some participant disagreed that mothers had not ever requested for CS without any medical indication in their experience whereas others shared of addressing very few of such cases, yet they manage to counsel them for NVD.

Table 9: Perception and Obstetric related factors

Characteristics	Category	n	Median	Mean rank	U/H value	p-value
Gravida	Primigravida	123	75	203.7	10446.500	<0.001*
	Multigravida	226	72	226		
Previous place of delivery	Home	34	63	84.50	2278	<0.001*
	Health Institution	315	74	184.77		
Previous mode of delivery	Normal	234	71	142.32	76.993	<0.001*
	Caesarean section	70	80	251.42		
	Normal and CS	37	77	220.59		
Previous pregnancy related problem	Yes	44	71	179.51	6511.500	0.751
	No	305	75	174.35		

U/H Value = Mann-Whitney Test/ Kruskal Wallis Test

Given table revealed that the median perception was found to be higher among primigravida women (75) with significance of $p < 0.001$. The median of perception was significantly higher among respondents who had previously delivered in health institution (74) compared to those with home deliveries (63), with a statistically significant difference ($p < 0.001$). Furthermore, women who had experienced CS only had highest perception while comparing the medians with significance of $p < 0.001$.

DISCUSSION

The study revealed that majority (59%) of respondents had adequate knowledge regarding caesarean section delivery. These findings was contradict with the study from Babcock University Teaching Hospital, Ogun State which showed that 78.5% had a high level of knowledge of CS.¹⁹ The gap in knowledge level could be due to differences in the study setting and also the higher level of education, as the majority of the respondents (58%) had up to the tertiary level of education in this study. Similarly, the odds of having adequate knowledge were 1.689 ($p=0.09$) times higher among primigravida women than those of Multigravida. In contrast, a study from Saudi Arabia reveals a significant association between the number of pregnancies and the knowledge score ($p=0.003$), showing higher the number of pregnancies, the greater the mother's awareness.¹⁴ Upon the multivariate logistic regression mode, it revealed that women experiencing CS at least once in their lifetime are more likely to have adequate knowledge than those experiencing NVD. The findings align with a comparative study conducted among pregnant of United Arab Emirates.²⁰

This study depicted, almost one third (32.9%) had experienced Caesarean section. Among which, the primary reasons for going through CS was Emergency indications (62.6%) and doctor's suggestion (22.6%). A study from tertiary care hospital of Nepal reported a prevalence of 36.8%,²¹ while in contrast, findings from district hospital in Illam indicated a prevalence of 14.70%.²²

In this study, comparing the medians, higher perception was found among the group of respondents who have experienced CS (80) than the group who had only normal vaginal delivery (71) which was statistically significant ($p<0.001$). It was similar to the findings of relevant study on perception of pregnant women of Nigeria which revealed that the respondents who had experienced CS have a more positive perception towards CS than the group who haven't.¹⁵ Only 2.9% of participants responded on choosing CS as a mode of delivery. Similarly lower preference for CS was reported in the other studies conducted in Nepal.^{23,24}

Exploring women's perception, a significant majority (94.9%) agreed that women recovers faster in vaginal delivery while 63.7% disagreed with idea of choosing CS as a child birth plan to avoid the extreme pain associated with NVD. With conflicting to this result, a qualitative study from Thailand disclosed women's perspective as, CS is an easy childbirth plan; it prevents women from encountering several challenges; facilitates time management and balances private lives among physicians as well.²⁵

Similarly, a qualitative study among obstetricians in rural Bangladesh claimed that private clinics were using their agents, known locally as 'dalals' (brokers) to take the birthing women away from public hospitals, sometimes the service providers in the primary health facility refer birthing women to the higher facility without any valid medical indication.¹⁷ *Likewise, the healthcare providers stated that private hospitals have been performing more caesarean section deliveries. The lack of proper labor monitoring, inadequate staffing, lack of motivation within available staffs at private health facilities and acceptance of maternal request for CS were reported as possible reasons.* It shows the similarity of worldwide increasing trend of CS from private hospitals, which might be due to profit oriented motive of hospital management, doctor's convenience and acceptance of maternal request. The National Policy on SBAs which was endorsed in 2006 has identified the importance of SBAs being present at every birth.²⁶

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, majority of respondents had adequate knowledge of CS delivery. The knowledge level was significantly associated with Religion, education of respondents, their permanent residence, gravida, previous mode of delivery and previous place of delivery. The study suggests that that respondents who had previous Health institution delivery had better knowledge than with previous home delivery. While exploring the median score of perception, it was found to be associated with the factors such as; Ethnicity, education of women, residence, preferred mode of delivery and preferred health institutions. The findings have highlighted that there were very few women who had preferred for CS as a mode of delivery. Though it interpreted higher prevalence of CS delivery among respondents. Furthermore, obstetricians emphasized the necessity for primary level health care workers to provide appropriate counseling to women during ANC visits about various modes of delivery, including their benefits and potential consequences.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Government at all levels should prioritize improving childbirth services, with the family welfare division closely monitoring cesarean section (CS) rates. Pregnant women must complete their antenatal care (ANC) visits, as proper counselling during these visits helps them understand delivery options and make informed decisions.

Limitations and future scope of the study

The findings of this study are limited by the exclusion of divorced and single mothers and the focus on healthcare providers in public hospitals, leaving out private sector perspectives.

To better understand maternal health challenges, researchers should include a wider range of participants, especially unmarried and divorced women. Future studies should also gather community-level data through focus groups and in-depth interviews, involving male participants as well.

Conflict of interests: The authors declare no conflict of interest

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Abbreviations

AOR	Adjusted Odds Ratio
CI	Confidence Interval
COR	Crude Odds Ratio
CS	Caesarean Section
KII	Key Informant Interview
NDHS	Nepal Demographic Health Survey
NVD	Normal Vaginal Delivery
SPSS	Statistical Package for Social Sciences
TOLAC	Trial of Labor After Caesarean
WHO	World Health Organization

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